

India's Transport and Transit Projects in Myanmar

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Abstract: The following write-up is about the four most important connectivity projects in Myanmar and beyond for which India has assisted. Despite a number of bottlenecks, the two of the projects are completed, two of them are yet to be completed. Anti-government forces operating in the ethnic minority inhabited areas are significantly slowing down the pace of progress of the projects.

In 1991, the Government of India led by Prime Minister Narasimha Rao adopted India's Look East Policy. The objective was to develop political, economic and security co-operation with countries of Southeast Asia. It wanted to make India an attractive destination for foreign aid and investment. ASEAN offered to fill its requirements. The new policy was a result of a post Cold War development. Of course in later years India also started balancing Chinese influence in the area.

After the adoption of the new foreign policy, India took several initiatives to improve its relationship with its immediate neighbours on a priority basis. One of the initiatives it took was to undertake several projects for improvement of transport and transit facilities with Myanmar for mutual benefit e.g. (i) up gradation and resurfacing of the 160 km. long Tamu-Kalewa-Kalemyo road; (ii) construction and up gradation of the Rhi-Tiddim Road in Myanmar; (iii) implementation of the Kaladan Multimodal Transport and Transit Project; and (iv) India-Myanmar-Thailand Trilateral Highway (IMT-TH) connectivity. This article examines various aspects associated with these projects including far reaching consequences on curbing insurgency in India's Northeast and Myanmar.

Taking up the first project, up gradation and resurfacing of the 160 km-long Tamu-Kalewa-Kalemyo road is the first major project undertaken by the Government of India in Myanmar. It was during the path breaking second visit (Dixit visited Myanmar in August 1992 also) of India's Foreign Secretary J. N. Dixit to Myanmar from 29 March to 1 April 1993¹, that India offered to upgrade the above road² from Tamu to Kalewa then to Kalemyo, the district Hq of Kale district of Sagaing region (previously called division).

The road runs quite close along the Indo-Myanmar border. Of course, it was an important one during the Second World War, used to regroup the troops deployed in the then Burma to retreat to the British Indian side towards Manipur when Japanese forces overran the country. Considering its importance, both countries underlined its up gradation and resurfacing in March 1993. The work of the Rs. 90-crore 160-km Tamu- Kalewa-Kalemyo road was thus

¹ Hindu (Chennai) 14 February 2001

² "India Myanmar Road Opened" Hindu (Chennai), 14 February 2001

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started sometime in 1997 by the Border Road Organisation (BRO) of India bringing, through Manipur, all the necessary construction materials from Dimapur, an important railhead in Nagaland. The project was funded entirely by the Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India. It took over three years to complete it.

The completion of the road was inaugurated on 13 February 2001 by India's External Affairs Minister, Jaswant Singh, in the presence of senior Ministers of Myanmar. He took also with him from Moreh, several Ministers from the north-eastern States. His visit was significant because no Indian Foreign Minister ever visited Myanmar since the visit of Atal Behari Vajpayee in 1977. From another angle, it was the first major project undertaken by India as a follow-up action of the goodwill visit of Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi in December 1987. The project which was successfully completed could, therefore, be regarded as the first symbol of improvement of relationship between the two countries since the strained relationship after the outbreak of the movement for the restoration of democracy. Highlighting its importance, the Myanmar Construction Minister, Major-General Saw Tun's message said, "This 100 miles stretch of road will become a vital section of the designated Asian Highway running from Singapore to Istanbul passing through Myanmar and India."³ . Speaking in Kalemmyo, the Myanmar Deputy Prime Minister and Military Affairs Minister, Lt. Gen. Tin Hla, said, "We celebrate not only the opening of a new road linking our two countries and the handing over of construction machinery for Monywa-Kalewa road (which will link Mandalay) but also the strengthening (of) the long-standing bonds of friendship existing between our two countries." He further said, "On our part, we are constructing a road from Monywa to Kalewa to link up with the new Tamu-Kalay (Kalemmyo) road... the new road is bound to bring about economic development to the border... we firmly believe that the cooperation between the Government (of) Myanmar and India will benefit our two peoples" . Most of these leaders were of the opinion that the road means that ordinary people can travel around freely, and goods and traffic movement, which used to take days, can now go through in a matter of hours.⁴ Most roads in Myanmar are utterly poor in maintenance.

Why connectivity with Kalemmyo is prioritized? It is because of the fact that the town was the hub of trading activity, which is now more with India across the border. It is well connected by a network of roads with Kalay, Gant Gaw, Monywa, Yarje and Mandalay. It is also connected by air with Mandalay and Yangon. Train service operates between Kalemmyo and Gunt Gaw. Inland water transport with Kalewa which is only 24 km away is another connectivity. Commuters from Kalemmyo can reach Mandalay both during rainy and winter seasons, though winter season is more convenient to travel. Over and above Kalemmyo today, has other facilities too like hospitals, modern system of communication including internet facility, simultaneous publication of newspapers and TV broadcast with Yangon, centres of higher education in the district attracting students from neighbouring areas including Haka, the capital city of the Chin state. The township is abound in rich natural resources like timber

³ Ibid.

⁴ Ibid.

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which are in great demand like teak, ironwood, valuable large timber varieties.⁵ Kalemio is an important city having an estimated population of 400,000. The majority are the Bamars who follow Theravada Buddhism and constitute around 55 per cent of it. The Chins are Baptists and constitute around 40 per cent of the population, and the rest are other nationalities including foreigners. The Kale district has not only 116 Buddhist monasteries, 508 churches, but also a mosque, two Hindu temples, a Chinese Communal temple. Buddhist seminaries, nunneries also exist. The multi-ethnic and multi-religious composition will attract tourists from India even. Although most of the population of the town is dependent on agriculture but it is also an industrial town. Different types of vehicles like cars, jeeps, trucks, fire engines, trailers, three-wheeled motorcycles are manufactured in the Kalay Industrial Estate.

Strategically, it is needless to point out that Myanmar's isolation during the military rule cut off the linkages with the outside world for decades. Economic decadence, decades old ethnic based insurgencies and the Communist movement, resulted in the declaration of the country as one of the Least Developed Countries in the world and became one of the poorest. On top of that a number of ethnic based insurgencies erupted at different times plus one of the longest hard fought communist movements exhausted not less than 40 per cent of Myanmar's GDP annually at one time in their attempts to curb insurgencies. Not only that insurgencies operating in India's Northeast took shelter, trained and operated from the bases from the Indo-Myanmar border areas, which were lightly controlled by the Yangon military authorities. Moreover, small arms brought by adventurous India origin insurgents through the Chittagong Hill Tracts, along the thick inhospitable hill terrain jungles of trans-border areas of Mizoram of India and the Chin State of Myanmar operated effectively in both Myanmar and India's Northeast taking advantage of inaccessibility and inadequate infrastructure in road transport.⁶ In short troop mobilization could not be done because of poor transport and communication of both the countries. That is why Hindu commented, "Another aspect of the road is that the response time of Myanmar security forces to Indian insurgents operating in the area is going to improve by leaps and bounds,"⁷

In view of this Jaswant Singh while speaking at Tamu, while inaugurating the road said that the construction was to facilitate cross border trade and help in economic development of the border areas of which beneficiaries would be Indian Northeasterners⁸ Jaswant Singh and other ministers of Myanmar viewed that the road would form a section of the future Asian Highway, would facilitate for people "to drive down from the Indian border to Mandalay".

⁵. India, Myanmar road opened, Mizzima News 13 Feb 2001.

⁶ 'Important Milestone' says Jaswant' Hindu (Chennai) 14 February 2001).

⁷ Ibid.

⁸ "Jaswant inaugurates India-Myanmar Road Link" National Herald (New Delhi), 14 February 2001

Whether it was exaggeration or not, Maung Aye, Secretary of the District Peace and Development Council thrilled to say, "The journey to Kalewa used to take two days. We can now be there in just two hours"⁹ and it was "on dirt road from Tamu to Kalewa", commented by *Pioneer* of New Delhi of 19 February. Last but not the least, inaccessibility and inadequate infrastructure caused to grow adventurous insurgents on both sides to roam freely with arms and act. Recounting his experiences, India's former Foreign Secretary and National Security Advisor J.N.Dixit wrote,

"The relationship, viewed in the background of China seeking to link up with ports in Myanmar through Mekong and Irrawaddy rivers and of China having logistical facilities for its navy on the southwestern coast of Myanmar, has obvious strategic and security implications for India". It is in this context that parallel to the Kunming-Lashio-Mandalay road India negotiated the construction of the Tamu-Kalewa- (Kalemyo) road which was inaugurated by Jaswant Singh during his February visit to Myanmar."¹⁰

2 Rhi –Tiddim Connectivity Project

Apart from the above up gradation and resurfacing of the Tamu-Kalewa-Kalemyo road, which is now more popularly known as Indo-Myanmar Friendship Road, there is another project which will benefit India's state of Mizoram. The joint communique issued during the visit of Senior General Than Swe to India from 25-29 July 2010 mentioned India to finance the construction and revamping of the Rhi-Tiddim in Myanmar. Rhi-Tiddim road will connect Tamu- Kalewa-Kalemyo road at Kalewa which will reach Mandalay, Myanmar's second biggest city. Further, this road will connect Mizoram's Champhai-Zawkhathar, the border trade point on the Indian side and Rhi sector on the Myanmar side. India agreed to finance through a grant assistance of US \$ 60 million. The project was finalized with the signing of an agreement during the visit of Shri SM Krishna, India's Minister of State for External Affairs to Myanmar from 20-22 June 2010. The completion of the project will not only benefit for trade and commerce but also satisfy as the Kuki-Chin Mizos believe that their souls rest in Rhi-Tiddim.¹¹ The present road from Kalemyo to Zokhawthar Land Custom Station in Mizoram via Tiddim is more of a kutchra road on which vehicles could ply only during the dry season. The opening of Indo-Myanmar border trade at Champhai- Zowkhathar and Rhi trade point, opened by Tawnluia, Home Minister of Mizoram on 30 January 2004 will promote people to people contact and promote border trade more vigorously. With the Indian assistance of US \$ 60 million the road is to be upgraded, at the moment, as a single lane to promote trade and travel links between Mizoram and Myanmar. Rhi-Tiddim road will connect Monywa beyond Kalemyo and finally Mandalay.

⁹ "India, Myanmar Set Out on a Highway Cooperation" Indian Express (New Delhi), 14 February 2001.

¹⁰ J.N.Dixit, "By Reviving the relationship with Myanmar, India has taken a Wise Step: A Matter of Security" Telegraph (Calcutta), 29 March 2001.)

¹¹ Myanmar Dictator to Get Warm Welcome in India, Business Standard (New Delhi), 19 July 2010.

3 Kaladan Project

The Kaladan Multi-Modal Transport and Transit Project (KMMTTP) is the third connectivity project undertaken by India in Myanmar. It envisages to connect India's Kolkata port with Myanmar's Sittwe deep sea port, the capital city of Myanmar's Rakhine State which will be by sea route covering a distance of 539 kms. The river Kaladan is navigable from its confluence point with the Bay of Bengal near Sittwe up to Setpyitpyin (Paletwa), Myanmar from where it will go to Kalewa covering a distance of 222 kms through waterway which is navigable. Beyond this the river is not navigable as the depth of water is shallow and the current of water is rapid. In view of this, transportation by road is proposed for this stretch. Then this proposed road will go to the Indo – Myanmar border covering another 62 kms and connect with India's national highway 54 in Mizoram. Handling point in India will be at Hmawngbu (Mobu) in Mizoram whereas handling point in Myanmar will be at Myeikwa¹². A 117 km. long two-lane highway is proposed to be constructed from Lawngtlai (Mizoram) to the Myanmar border to provide road linkage up to Hmawngbu (Mobu). Department of Road Transport and Highways (DORTH) proposes to construct a two-lane highway with 12m wide formation. The estimated cost is Rs.550 crores and is included in Phase-A of "Special Accelerated Road Development Programme in North East (SARDP-NE). SARDP-NE is an initiative taken up by the Ministry of Road Transport & Highways of the Government of India as a mega project. The scope of the programme has been expanded, from time to time, since September 2005. *Times of India* reported that a high power committee headed by Brahm Prakash, Secretary Road Transport and Highways cleared on 19 December a sum of Rs 560 crore¹³ The PWD of Mizoram is constructing the road.

The project activities of up gradation of port and waterway and construction of road from Kalewa to Indo-Myanmar border is expected to be completed by 2014-15. Inland Waterways Authority of India has been appointed as the Project Development Consultant by Ministry of External Affairs for the Myanmar portion. They are in the process of making the designs for the Myanmar portion.

The objective of the proposal is to provide an alternative access route to the land-locked North-Eastern region of India. The project is significant in view of severe pressure on the Siliguri Corridor and Bangladesh's continued intransigence in providing transit facilities through its territory to the North-East. Once completed the project is expected to benefit Mizoram, the peaceful state in the NE surrounded by troubled NE states.

How it is going to benefit Mizoram? Time taken to transport raw materials like bamboo, and the distance to be traversed will be drastically reduced. Huge bamboo resources can be transported from Mizoram to Kolkata to feed industries in West Bengal. It is said that the

¹² <http://www.mdoner.gov.in/content/introduction-1> downloaded on 10 .9.13.

¹³ See "To boost trade, govt Oks 100km NE Road" *Times of India* (New Delhi), 20 December 2009.

state of Mizoram covers with 6500 sq.kms with bamboos. The former Chief Minister of Mizoram Zoramthanga believed that this green gold will contribute to transform the state's economy.

Needless to say India and Myanmar negotiated for the project starting from 2003, had six rounds of talks but finalized only during the visit of Myanmar's Foreign Minister U Nyan Win to India in January 2008 where he met Pranab Mukherjee, India's minister of External Affairs in New Delhi. Following the visit India's Union Cabinet approved a sum of Rs. 535.91 crore for the project on 27 March 2008 under the "Aid to Myanmar" project for the up-gradation of Sittwe port and Kaladan Waterway. A part of the fund will be used for the construction of a road from Kalewa to the India – Myanmar border which will be of 62km long highway. The project is expected to be completed sometime in 2014 according to the Governor of Mizoram Vakkom Purushothaman .

The Kaladan project is financed by India's Ministry of External Affairs. Rail India Technical and Economic Services (RITES) carried out its feasibility study during 1999 – 2000 and submitted the report in March 2001. The Internal Authority of India will carry out construction work on Sittwe port and the jetty at Paletwa including dredging work with Essar Projects Ltd, a division of the Essar Group appointed in May 2010 as the main contractor.

The development of the Kaladan project is divided into three main phases. First, the port needs its expansion and the construction of a new inland waterway terminal (IWT) to accommodate larger vessels and an increasing volume shipping traffic and two jetties- a bigger and a smaller one. The larger jetty of the size of 219x15 m is expected to handle 20,000 ton ships while the other smaller one of the size of 54x15 is meant for smaller vessels that will ply along the Kaladan river. The present jetty is of the size of 78x15 m. In view of this, it is said that large scale dredging is required. The work on the port began in December 2010 and is expected to be completed by the middle of this year. The Detailed Engineering Report (DER) of the road project is expected to be finalized this year.¹⁴

In the second phase dredging is required of 225km of the Kaladan River between Sittwe and Setpyitpyin (Paletwa) in Chin State where another terminal will be built. Finally, as mentioned earlier construction of a 62 km highway between Setpyitpyin (Kaletwa) and the Mizoram border of India is also planned.

Originally, the first and second phases of the project were to begin before the end of 2009. However, construction started only in November 2010. The development of phases 1 and 2 in Sittwe, the river dredging and the inland waterways terminal (IWT) at Kaletwa were primarily executed by the state-run Inland Waterways Authority of India with Essar Projects Ltd, Mumbai (a division of the Essar Group appointed in May 2010 as the main contractor).

¹⁴ Kaladan Project should benefit India, Myanmar: Pressure groups see http://articles.timesofindia.indiatimes.com/2013-06-12/guwahati/39924133_1_kaladan-project-sittwe-myanmar downloaded on 26 November.2013.

Both Rail India Rechnical and Economic Service (RITES) and Inland Waterways Authority of India (IWAI) are state-run Indian companies. But the third phase of highway construction will be headed by the Myanmar Ministry of Transport. The construction of the highway from Paletwa to the India-Burma border was originally scheduled to start from the year 2011-12. However, the construction has now been delayed though the foundation laying ceremony was held on 19 December 2010. The entire project is planned to be completed in three years, with work suspended for five to six months of the year due to the monsoon.¹⁵ However, delay in its completion caused revision of the cost estimate from its earlier amount of Rupees 535.91 crore to 2904.04 crore. The Union Cabinet chaired by Prime Minister Narendra Modi approved it on 14 October 2015 quoted a PIB source.¹⁶

Even though it was revised with high hopes, the Arakan Army, an anti-government rebel group in Myanmar, captured Paletwa, an important site in the Kaladan project in January 2024, making the continuance of the Kaladan project difficult to progress said a *Hindu* source.¹⁷

4 The India–Myanmar–Thailand Trilateral Highway (IMT-TH)

Apart from the above 3 important projects, The India–Myanmar–Thailand trilateral Highway (IMT-TH) is a mega connectivity project of India, Myanmar and Thailand. The idea of constructing a trilateral highway starting from India to Thailand through Myanmar covering many important centres of trade and commerce in Myanmar was first proposed by former Prime Minister Atal Bihari Vajpayee. This India–Myanmar–Thailand trilateral Highway (IMT-TH) connects Moreh in Manipur, India and Mae Sot in Thailand via Mandalay and Naypyidaw in Myanmar.

The 1,400-kilometer highway begins in Moreh in India's Manipur state, passes through Myanmar, and ends at Mae Sot in Thailand. The project was approved at an India-Myanmar-Thailand ministerial-level meeting in 2002 in April held in Yangon. Foreign Ministers of three countries Jaswant Singh of India, U Win Aung of Myanmar, and Dr Surakiart Sathirathai of Thailand represented their countries.¹⁸ Construction began in 2012, and now around 70 percent of the project has been completed as reported in September 2023.

¹⁵ <https://pwnlyias.com/current-affairs/kaladan-project/> downloaded on 19 March 2024

¹⁶“Kaladan Multi Transport Project revised to Rs 2904.04 cr: More boost Act East Policy” Sangai Express (Imphal) 15 October 2015

¹⁷<https://pwnlyias.com/current-affairs/kaladan-project/> downloaded on 19 March 2024

¹⁸ Text of the Press Release issued on the Occasion of the India-Myanmar-Thailand Ministerial Meeting on the Transport Linkages, Yangon, Myanmar, 5-6 April 2002.

The IMT-TH presents a significant opportunity for enhanced connectivity and regional integration. It aims to connect India's Northeast region with Thailand via Myanmar, facilitating trade and commerce, health, education, and tourism between the three nations while providing a more efficient and cost-effective transportation route. India has proposed extending the road network to include Cambodia, Laos, and Vietnam, further expanding its reach and potential impact. Bangladesh is also interested in joining the initiative for enhancing trade links and tourism.

The total length of the highway is 1360 km. Since its conception in 2002, the Trilateral Highway project has faced various delays and challenges. Political instability in Myanmar and financial issues have been the most important bottlenecks. India's External Affairs Minister emphasised the importance of peace and stability in border areas, expressed concerns about trafficking, reiterated India's support for Myanmar's democratic transition, proposed people-centric initiatives to address pressing challenges, and aimed to closely coordinate its policy with ASEAN regarding Myanmar.¹⁹

Here it may not be out of place to mention that the project aims to establish an essential strategic route, but earlier targets for its operationalisation have been delayed. Initially, the government sought to make the highway operational by 2015 and then extended the timeline till 2019. Now, the new deadline is set for 2027. It is, thus, crucial to closely assess the current situation on the ground to gauge the progress of this delayed project. The IMT-TH project follows a proposed plan that starts from Bangkok and passes through cities like Sukhothai and Mae Sot in Thailand, and Yangon, Mandalay, Kalewa, and Tamu in Myanmar before reaching India. In India, it is likely to pass through Moreh, Kohima, Guwahati, Srirampur, Siliguri, and Kolkata, running over 2,800 km. The longest stretch of the highway will be in India.

Detailing persisting bottlenecks, Sreeparna Bannerjee writes,

The IMT-TH project encompasses a vital road network in Myanmar, which, despite having witnessed notable development in recent times, still needs progress at numerous stretches. Several sections of the original IMT-TH alignments have been completed or upgraded, including the crucial bypass road connecting Myawaddy and Kawkareik in Thailand and the second friendship bridge linking Myawaddy and Mae Sot. Additionally, ongoing efforts involve the improvement and repair of roads between Kalewa (India) and Monywa (Myanmar), the construction of a new Bago bridge supported by Japan, and the development of an arterial road connecting Bago and Kyaukse in Myanmar, facilitated by the Asian Development Bank (ADB). However, urgent attention is required to replace 69 bridges along the Tamu-Kyigone-Kalewa road. Work on this stretch has been delayed since 2015 due to the

¹⁹Sreeparna Bannerjee, "Enhancing connectivity and regional integration: The India-Myanmar-Thailand Trilateral Highway project" Expert Speak Raisina Debates, Observer Research Foundation, published on 28 July 2023.

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termination of the contractor's agreement. Recently, reports suggest that work on the first bridge between Moreh (in Manipur) and Tamu (in Myanmar) is expected to restart soon. However, a proper timeline is needed. Construction is underway on the difficult Yar Gyi road section, a significant part of the Trilateral Highway. This particular stretch is characterised by steep gradients and sharp curves, posing considerable challenges to the construction process. Currently, only about 25 percent of the road is complete. The Trade Minister of Myanmar has indicated that converting a 121.8-km portion of the road, specifically between Kalewa and Yar Gyi, into a four-lane motorway will require more time than anticipated. Consequently, the construction team may need to extend or postpone the initial deadline for completion.²⁰

Additionally, Sreeparna highlights the ongoing conflict between the Junta and the ethnic armed groups operating in the Chin State and Sagaing Region of Myanmar. If the conditions do not subside, the resumption of work by contractors seems improbable. Another aspect that needs immediate attention is formulating and implementing the IMT Trilateral Motor Vehicle Agreement (IMT-TMVA). Added to this bureaucratic hurdles continue to remain a significant bottleneck, where obtaining permits and clearances remains challenging due to differences in the rules and procedures of vehicle movement in each nation making the situation time-consuming and cumbersome. On top of that, the security situation in Myanmar is also a significant concern for the implementation of the IMT-TMVA. The country has faced political instability and conflict in recent years, which has affected road transport safety. There have been reports of attacks on vehicles and disruption of transport routes, which can be a significant risk for businesses and travellers. This has led to concerns about the safety of drivers and passengers, which may impact the viability of any agreement.

India's commitment to supporting Myanmar's democratic transition process and its emphasis on peace and stability are integral to the region's progress and prosperity. Strengthening policy coordination with ASEAN regarding Myanmar will contribute to a more holistic approach to regional issues and ensure a stable environment for connectivity projects to thrive. Overall, the successful completion of the India-Myanmar-Thailand Trilateral Highway hopes to not only bolster economic growth but also pave the way for more robust regional integration, cultural exchange, and cooperation among the participating nations, ultimately contributing to peace, stability, and prosperity in the Mekong-Ganga region, writes Sreeparna.²¹

Significantly, India's Ministry of External Affairs recently acknowledged the slow pace of bilateral projects. In its annual report of 2022, it specifically mentioned that the pace of implementation of large infrastructure projects has suffered due to the security situation in

²⁰Ibid.

²¹ Ibid.

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Myanmar including the Kaladan Multimodal Transit Transport Project and the India-Myanmar-Thailand Trilateral Highway Project.²²

Foreign Secretary paid a working visit to Nay Pyi Taw, Myanmar on 20-21 November 2022 and held discussions on security and stability in the border areas, and reviewed bilateral cooperation. Again, recently, at the concluding 12th Mekong Ganga Cooperation (MGC) meeting held in Bangkok on 16 July 2023, Indian External Affairs Minister Dr. S. Jaishankar met with his Myanmar counterpart U Than Swe discussed regional connectivity initiatives, with particular emphasis on expediting the India-Myanmar-Thailand Trilateral Highway (IMT-TH) project.

It is noteworthy that India's development assistance in Myanmar is about USD 2 billion, the bulk of which is grants. Major people-centric projects include the Kaladan Multimodal Transit Transport Project, the India-Myanmar-Thailand Trilateral Highway Project, the Border Area Development Programme in Chin State and the Naga Self-Administered Zone; assistance in setting up institutions for higher learning and research, namely Myanmar Institute of Information Technology (MIIT), Advanced Centre for Agricultural Research and Education (ACARE), Myanmar-India Centre for Enhancement of IT Skills (MICEITS); India-Myanmar Industrial Training Centres (ITC); Rakhine State Development Programme; the repair and conservation of earthquake damaged pagodas etc. Not only that India extended humanitarian assistance. It provided support to Myanmar in its fight against Covid-19 through supply of medicines, medical equipment and vaccines through 2021 and 2022. Towards this end, two medical oxygen plants were supplied to Myanmar in January 2022. In total, India has supplied more than 21 million doses of Covid-19 vaccine to Myanmar, including as gift and commercial supplies. In essence, in the last two decades or so India's relationship with Myanmar is growing despite the existence of a number of security concerns.

²² Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, Annual Report, 2022, (New Delhi) pp.45-47.

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